

In Silico Methodologies in Computational Medicine: from Complex Disease Modeling to Virtual Clinics

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Computational medicine leverages *in silico* methodologies, grounded in biophysical principles, to model, understand, and control complex diseases across multiple spatial and temporal scales. This review provides a comprehensive overview of the conceptual foundations and of a structured workflow—a general *modus operandi*—that guides these investigations. We discuss key modeling approaches, ranging from bioinformatics, network medicine, and systems biology to mechanobiological models, interpretable machine learning, and simulations. Central to translating these tools is the virtual clinic framework, encompassing virtual patients, digital twins, and virtual cohorts, whose utility relies on rigorous parameter identification, multimodal data integration, and systematic validation. We examine the challenges of developing models that are simultaneously informative, predictive, tractable, and clinically relevant, and highlight how *in silico* approaches can personalize medicine, optimize treatment strategies, de-risk clinical trials, reduce costs, and address ethical concerns. Finally, we critically evaluate the advantages and limitations of the field—from multi-scale predictive power to data dependency and regulatory hurdles—and outline emerging trends in high-resolution data integration, machine learning, and model-based control. This review aims to offer both a structured framework for newcomers and a critical, forward-looking perspective on the evolving role of how *in silico* methodologies are accelerating translational research and improving patient outcomes.

Topics: Bioinformatics, complexity science, computational models for complex diseases, data-driven and physically-based models, disease control, machine learning, network medicine, phenomenological and physiological models, systems biology, structured workflow, virtual clinic

CONTENTS			
I. Introduction	1	D. Virtual cohorts	18
II. <i>In silico</i> and computational medicine	2	E. Validation	19
III. A general structured workflow	3	F. Virtual analysis	19
IV. Complex disease modeling	4	G. Virtual control	20
1. Bioinformatics	5	H. Examples	20
2. Network Medicine	6	VII. Discussion and conclusions	21
3. Systems Biology	7	Author Declarations	22
4. Mechanobiology	9	Conflict of interest statement	22
5. Black-Box Medicine	10	Acknowledgements	22
6. Interpretable machine learning	11	References	23
7. Simulation techniques	12	I. INTRODUCTION	
8. The <i>in silico</i> continuum: a unifying conceptual framework	13	Medicine increasingly confronts complex, multi-scale diseases characterized by multifactorial causation, non-linear dynamics, and profound patient-specific variability across molecular, cellular, tissue, and organism levels. While traditional <i>in vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> studies remain indispensable, they are constrained by ethical boundaries, high costs, low scalability, and the inability to systematically explore vast parameter spaces or hypothetical clinical scenarios. To overcome these	
V. Challenge: what makes a model valuable?	16		
VI. Virtual clinic	17		
A. Virtual patient models	17		
B. Data required	17		
C. Virtual patients and digital twins	18		

limitations, the exponential growth of biomedical data and computational power has propelled *in silico* methodologies into essential components of biomedical research and clinical decision support^{1,2}. Crucially, because biological systems are governed by fundamental physical laws, *in silico* medicine provides the required mathematical architecture to formalize biophysical constraints—such as cellular thermodynamics, transport phenomena, mass conservation, and mechanical force transduction—enabling researchers to investigate pathological disruptions and optimize treatment dynamics.

Over the past two decades, these computational approaches have evolved from isolated bioinformatics or systems biology tools into integrated, multi-physics frameworks capable of simulating disease mechanisms, predicting therapeutic responses, and optimizing clinical trials³. These methodologies span mechanistic, physics-based formulations to data-driven artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) architectures, increasingly unified within a continuum *in silico* framework. Consequently, computational medicine has emerged as a highly interdisciplinary field bridging medicine, biology, physics, mathematics, engineering, and computer science. Although several previous reviews have addressed isolated components of *in silico* medicine, such as digital twins and virtual patient frameworks⁴, multiscale computational modeling⁵, verification, validation, and uncertainty quantification in regulatory-oriented *in silico* trials⁶, or physics-informed and machine learning-based methodologies⁷, these works often focus on relatively narrow methodological perspectives or specific translational domains. In contrast, this review delivers a unified framework and taxonomy that connects these heterogeneous paradigms—from complex disease modeling to virtual patient-based virtual clinics—emphasizing their methodological interdependencies, validation requirements, personalized treatment optimization, and translational workflows.

Despite their potential, *in silico* methods remain fragmented across disciplines, exhibiting heterogeneous modeling assumptions, varied validation rigor, and diverse degrees of interpretability, which hinders model reuse and clinical translation. As computational architectures grow in complexity, establishing model credibility and managing decision-making risk become critical challenges⁸, particularly when navigating the trade-off between over-simplifying biophysical systems and over-parameterizing clinical models. To address this, the community relies on formal model credibility, defined as the trust in the predictive capability of a computational model for a specific context of use (COU)⁹. Rooted in engineering verification, validation, and uncertainty quantification (VVUQ) standards—notably the ASME V&V 40 and FDA guidelines^{9,10}—verification confirms the accurate mathematical implementation of the model, while validation evaluates its predictive fidelity against real-world data. Crucially, uncertainty quantification maps input variabilities to define robust confidence intervals for clinical predictions¹⁰, bridging the gap between theoretical modeling, regulatory trust, and personalized precision medicine.

This paper provides a structured, workflow-oriented overview of *in silico* methodologies in computational

medicine. Rather than offering an exhaustive chronological survey, the literature is organized according to methodological paradigms to outline the operational pipeline from complex disease modeling to the implementation of the virtual clinic. We examine the distinct advantages and clinical drawbacks, concluding with a comprehensive discussion on current regulatory challenges, emerging technological directions, and future translational perspectives.

II. IN SILICO AND COMPUTATIONAL MEDICINE

Modern biomedical research increasingly integrates traditional *in vivo*, *in vitro*, and *ex vivo* paradigms with advanced computational workflows. *In silico* studies leverage high-performance computing to model, analyze, and simulate complex biological processes, formalizing experimental hypotheses into mathematical or algorithmic representations that can be systematically interrogated and validated¹¹. Specifically, *in silico* medicine emphasizes mechanistic modeling, physics-based virtual experimentation, and patient-specific simulations governed by biophysical principles—such as mass transport, fluid dynamics, and cellular energetics—to decode disease mechanisms and predict therapeutic outcomes¹. This focus represents a distinct, mechanistically grounded subset of the broader domain of computational medicine, encompassing all data-driven techniques, statistical learning, ML, and AI architectures applied to biomedical data, often prioritizing phenomenological correlations over explicit physical laws^{12,13}.

The historical evolution of this field—transitioning from early cellular automata frameworks and localized multi-scale applications, such as *in silico* radiation oncology^{14,15}, to modern genome-wide simulations—was accelerated by the convergence of high-throughput multi-omics data and exponential leaps in computational power. Today, *in silico* medicine represents a profound paradigm shift in biomedical research, complementing and, in specific domains, transforming traditional experimental and clinical methodologies⁸. According to the epistemological framework introduced by Thomas Kuhn¹⁶, scientific disciplines progress through periods of normal science governed by an established paradigm, which eventually encounters anomalies that cannot be resolved within the existing rules. This mismatch triggers a state of crisis, leading to a scientific revolution that replaces the legacy framework with a new paradigm. In modern medicine, this crisis is manifested in the limitations of traditional reductionist approaches, such as the poor clinical translation of animal models and the inability to predict highly non-linear, patient-specific biophysical interactions. In this context, *in silico* medicine embodies a fundamental shift in the foundational concepts and experimental practices of medicine, positioning computational models as primary instruments to understand, predict, and treat disease.

FIG. 1. Iterative and interdisciplinary structured workflow in research for *in silico* and computational medicine, from research questions and available data to model development, simulations, interpretation, and experimental validation. Dashed arrows indicate optional feedback loops enabling improvements repeating the entire workflow (refinement cycle) or a few parts of the workflow, such as in model development and validation.

III. A GENERAL STRUCTURED WORKFLOW

In silico medicine relies on cross-disciplinary synergy, integrating mathematics, engineering, life sciences, and computer science under clinical guidance¹⁷. Its success requires close collaboration among clinicians, data scientists, software engineers, and regulatory specialists to guarantee clinical relevance, reproducibility, and compliance^{1,18–20}.

This interdisciplinary cooperation is paramount during model design, where complex biological mechanisms must be mathematically formalized without violating physical laws. To transition from a general data-science pipeline to a scientifically rigorous biomedical framework, the workflow must incorporate established VVUQ standards^{9,21} and model credibility assessment frameworks^{8,19}. A structured workflow embedding data governance and metadata standards (e.g., FAIR principles) ensures that inputs remain findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable²². This approach facilitates iterative hypothesis refinement, data analysis, model validation, and healthcare protocol optimization, and addresses domain-specific challenges such as parameter identifiability and regulatory considerations, facilitating the assessment of whether a model is fit-for-purpose within its specific context of use^{8,9,21}. Furthermore, the workflow must be intentionally designed to streamline validation²³, addressing the critical shortage of rigorously validated predictive models in current literature²⁴.

While adaptable to specific research questions, the standard *in silico* operational pipeline is illustrated in Fig. 1 and detailed below.

- 1. Define the research question and context of use.** Formulate clear clinical or physiological objectives. The context of use defines the specific role and scope of the model in the decision-making process^{9,21}. This foundation guides paradigm selection, data requirements, validation endpoints, and the risk-informed level of credibility required for regulatory acceptance^{1,19}.
- 2. Data collection.** Gather experimental, literature, or database information. Ensure data quality, consistent annotation, and characterize data uncertainty, as it directly impacts model credibility²².
- 3. Data preprocessing and preparation.** Clean, normalize, filter, and anonymize data (e.g., GDPR compliance²⁵). Document pipelines to ensure reproducibility and assess how data transformations might introduce bias or obscure biological variability¹².
- 4. Define assumptions and simplification.** Explicitly document all biological assumptions and simplifications—such as spatial dimensionality reduction or continuum approximations—assessing their impact via sensitivity analysis to balance reductionism and holism to achieve predictive personalized models²⁶.
- 5. Model formulation and verification.** Formulate mathematical or computational architectures aligned with the intended use, ensuring that constitutive equations respect fundamental biophysical laws. Implement code and calculation verification (VVUQ) to ensure the mathematical equations are solved correctly before biological validation begins⁹. Establish the target credibility level to guide subsequent regulatory-aligned validation^{8,19}.
- 6. Model calibration and identifiability.** Optimize parameters against observed data, or train ML models while preventing overfitting and data leakage. Perform a formal identifiability analysis to ensure that model parameters—especially unmeasurable biophysical parameters—can be uniquely determined from the available data, reporting all calibration uncertainties^{12,26}.
- 7. Model validation and uncertainty assessment.** Evaluate predictive utility against independent datasets within the defined context of use (prospective validation). Assess model credibility by evaluating the rigor of the verification, validation, uncertainty and error quantification, and robustness to biases^{19,27}, fulfilling key requirements for regulatory acceptance^{1,8,20}.
- 8. Integration with experimental validation.** Execute targeted experiments to systematically challenge *in silico* predictions. This iterative feedback loop enhances structural robustness, translational relevance, uncertainty quantification, and overall model confidence^{1,9}.
- 9. Analyses and simulations of prospective scenarios.** Run simulations to explore hypothetical what-if scenarios, optimize therapeutic protocols, and generate predictions. Secure reproducibility through code/data versioning, maintaining numerical stability, containerization, and public archiving²².
- 10. Interpretation of results and uncertainty quantification.** Examine outputs in the context of research objectives. Use visualization and statistical analyses to communicate insights, report results with explicit uncertainty intervals, and support robust interpretation²⁶.
- 11. Evaluation and refinement.** Critically evaluate performance against boundaries of applicability. Evaluate if the model meets the pre-defined credibility goals

to guide iterative model improvements and document residual biases or the domain of applicability^{1,18,19}.

12. **Iteration and further analysis.** Repeat steps to reduce parameter uncertainty or address new clinical queries. For deployed solutions, establish continuous post-market monitoring and re-validation protocols to ensure tracking and adherence to evolving regulatory frameworks^{20,28}.

IV. COMPLEX DISEASE MODELING

This section evaluates the computational methodologies deployed to architect *in silico* models of complex diseases, delineating the operational criteria for their selection, timing, and implementation. The paradigm shift toward high-fidelity computational modeling is driven by the simultaneous convergence of high-performance computing architectures, high-throughput multi-omics repositories, and advanced statistical mechanics. Modern life sciences have transitioned from descriptive biology toward quantitative disciplines capable of interrogating human health at unprecedented resolution¹⁷. Within this framework, multi-modal data availability acts as the primary substrate for parameter calibration, inverse problem regularization, and prospective predictive simulations. Rapid advancements in high-resolution analytical methods routinely yield vast, high-dimensional datasets; consequently, bioinformatics and biostatistics have become indispensable to extract latent mechanistic features from biological noise, leveraging computational tools such as ML and AI to bypass traditional analytical constraints.

To address the challenges of multi-scale complexity and high-dimensional data interpretation, *in silico* medicine leverages an interconnected ecosystem of computational, statistical, and mechanistic paradigms. These core methodologies—spanning bioinformatics, network medicine, systems biology, discrete simulations, and data-driven black-box methods where predictive models generate outputs from data without explicitly representing the underlying biological mechanisms—are systematically synthesized in Table I. Concurrently, developments in computational systems biology have enhanced the mechanistic simulation of biological topologies, formalizing processes extending from sub-cellular kinetics—such as genetic alterations²⁹, signaling pathways³⁰, and molecular docking³¹—to macroscopic cellular fates, including duplication, death, migration, angiogenesis, and the spatiotemporal emergence of heterogeneity and evolutionary dynamics³². At the organismal scale, these unified architectures effectively capture complex disease dynamics, as demonstrated in mathematical models of cancer³³, COVID-19³⁴, and restless legs syndrome³⁵, providing the formal algorithms, data structures, and visualization suites required to translate static biological observations into predictive, experimentally testable hypotheses³⁶.

Network science offers the fundamental mathematical frameworks to study complex biological topologies, mapping intracellular signaling communication, multi-scale agent in-

FIG. 2. Scopus search of “*in silico* medicine” (accessed on 28/01/2026): (a) annual number of publications (up to 2025) and (b) overall distribution by subject area.

teractions (cells, neurons, and populations), algorithmic neural networks, and temporal graphs^{37–40}. Formalized under the term Network Medicine, this approach identifies cellular interactomes, disease-disease networks, and social contact graphs as key levels of biological interaction governing pathobiology⁴¹. Complementing these topological networks, systems and control theory provides a rigorous formal approach to explore non-linear spatio-temporal behaviors and mathematically optimize therapeutic interventions. To bridge individual scales, multi-scale modeling integrates processes extending from genetic regulation to whole-organ physiology, and from nanosecond molecular dynamics to years-long clinical progression, addressing the core challenges of holistic biomedical modeling.

Discrete and hybrid modeling paradigms, such as agent-based models (ABMs) and cellular automata (CA), explicitly formalize local stochastic interactions, cellular crowding, and spatial heterogeneity at the single-entity level, capturing microscopic boundary effects that are mathematically intractable within continuum formulations^{42–46}. Conversely, non-mechanistic or black-box methods predict system behavior using empirical input-output data streams without explicit system descriptions. Techniques such as autoregressive–moving-average (ARMA) time-series models (statistical methods used to describe temporal dependencies in sequential data), artificial neural networks, and deep learning algorithms excel at identifying implicit predictive rules within novel data⁴⁷. To mitigate data opacity, interpretable machine learning approaches—including explainable AI, causal discovery, causal inference⁴⁸, and physics-informed neural networks (PINNs)⁴⁹—actively embed foundational physical constraints into statistical models to enhance transparency and clinical trust.

Finally, evolutionary theory provides the overarching biological logic that unifies these diverse scales, underpinning computational models of adaptation, clonal selection, genomic drift, and evolvability⁵⁰. By leveraging modeling techniques such as evolutionary game theory, replicator dynamics, fitness landscape analysis, and adaptive dynamics⁵¹, researchers can formalize the selection pressures governing both cellular-scale drug resistance and population-scale epidemiological shifts. Classical statistical paradigms—including survival analysis, nonparametric inference, and Bayesian statistics—remain foundational for model parameterization

and clinical data interpretation. Increasingly, these distinct paradigms are hybridized, allowing researchers to seamlessly couple statistical data power with the deterministic boundary conditions of mechanistic modeling to achieve a unified, multi-scale perspective on human pathobiology⁴². This comprehensive landscape has garnered substantial interest within the scientific community, as reflected in the exponential growth and interdisciplinary breadth of the literature illustrated in Figure 2.

We present these core methodologies in parallel, ultimately highlighting their interconnected relationships through the conceptual framework of the *in silico* continuum. Crucially, each computational paradigm detailed below follows a uniform structure that delineates its foundational definition, core workflow and strengths, technical boundaries, and clinical translational readiness alongside a quantified representative example.

1. Bioinformatics

Bioinformatics is an interdisciplinary field of science that develops computational methods and software tools for understanding biological data, especially in context of large and complex datasets. It constitutes the foundational layer of *in silico* medicine, providing the quantitative and computational framework to decode molecular complexity and high-dimensional biological data⁵².

a. Methodological workflow and strengths The typical methodological workflow begins with raw data processing from Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS) platforms^{53,54} to quantify gene and protein expression profiles across different biological states. Downstream of sequencing, sequence-alignment algorithms like STAR⁵⁵, BLAST⁵⁶, HMMER⁵⁷, and SAM⁵⁸ identify homologous regions and structural motifs. For downstream biological interpretation, functional annotation frameworks assign biological meaning to these molecular features using standardized vocabularies. This step enables the programmatic analysis of cellular organization and active biological pathways by mapping altered sequences to structured networks like Gene Ontology (GO)⁵⁹ or the Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG)⁶⁰.

The primary strength of bioinformatics lies in its unparalleled capacity to process, reduce, and interpret massive, high-dimensional datasets characterized by thousands of variables measured simultaneously for each sample, effectively translating raw molecular sequences into structured biological knowledge by integrating them with curated prior knowledge encoded in pathways or cell-type signatures.

b. Technical limitations and failures Despite its maturity, bioinformatics faces severe technical hurdles, starting with data bias and overfitting. Functional annotation frameworks (which assign biological meaning to genomic regions) and curated databases like the KEGG⁶⁰ or Gene Ontology (GO)⁵⁹ are highly dependent on the quality of the input data; consequently, sequencing noise, low depth, or uncorrected batch effects frequently propagate through the pipeline, leading to false-positive associations in biomarker identifica-

tion. Furthermore, a critical limitation is parameter identifiability in structural bioinformatics^{61,62}: in *ab initio* protein structure prediction (where conformations are predicted from physicochemical principles without homologous templates) and molecular dynamics simulations⁶², the vast and rugged energy landscape creates a massive search space with multiple local minima, making the identification of the correct, biologically active state mathematically underdetermined without significant and often unavailable experimental constraints.

c. Appropriate use cases and recommended contexts Bioinformatics approaches are highly successful and strongly recommended in early-stage drug discovery⁶³, target identification, and structure-based drug design. In these specific contexts, cheminformatics tools^{64,65} efficiently apply computational and statistical methods to chemical and pharmacological data, enabling researchers to screen virtual libraries and accurately predict small-molecule interactions, ADMET profiles, and binding affinities before physical synthesis.

d. Failures and non-recommended contexts Conversely, pure bioinformatics methods fail or are not recommended when applied to complex, multi-factorial diseases where pathophysiology is driven by dynamic, non-linear gene-environment interactions (such as lifestyle-induced epigenetics) rather than static genetic sequence variants. Because tools like MEGA^{29,66,67} offer a static snapshot or a historical evolutionary view of biological sequences, they inherently lack the mechanistic capacity to capture time-resolved interaction maps, metabolic fluxes, or systemic physiological feedbacks, leading to a total lack of generalization when shifting from instantaneous molecular lists to organism-level disease progression.

e. Clinical translation and current status Currently, the clinical translation of bioinformatics is highly mature in oncology and rare disease diagnostics, where standardized pipelines for variant calling and roadmaps are routinely used to select targeted therapies^{68,69}. However, its translation into general chronic disease management remains a major challenge due to the difficulty of translating statistical associations (e.g., a list of differentially expressed genes) into actionable, mechanistic clinical interventions.

f. Illustrative example: clinical whole-genome sequencing for solid tumors A representative case of modern clinical translation that bridges these descriptive limitations is the prospective study conducted by Kim *et al.*⁷⁰, which evaluated the real-world clinical utility of a comprehensive bioinformatics pipeline for whole-genome sequencing (WGS) of solid tumors. In this work, the authors implemented an end-to-end clinical bioinformatics framework (using the CancerVision pipeline) on a cohort of 120 patients to process matched tumor-normal tissue data. The bioinformatic workflow successfully bypassed descriptive sequence-listing failures by integrating raw variant calling with automated annotations of tumor mutational burden and somatic mutational signatures. Strikingly, the pipeline achieved a 79% reporting success rate within a median of 11 working days, delivering clinically relevant insights for 72% of the analyzed patients. The clinical impact was direct: 69% of cases yielded immediate therapeutic actionability (and 81% (13/16) pertaining to clinical

clarity), allowing for the informed selection of targeted therapeutics and the recruitment of patients into active, biomarker-stratified clinical trials.

2. Network Medicine

Network medicine^{37,41} applies network science and topology to identify, prevent, and treat human diseases. Rather than focusing on isolated components, this discipline models pathologies as emergent properties governed by the structural architecture and global dynamics of biological graphs, spanning from intracellular networks to disease-factor associations, such as contacts in epidemiology.

a. Methodological workflow and strengths The core methodological workflow relies on mapping the interactome, i.e., the complete set of molecular interactions within a biological system, through PPI and metabolic pathways, as well as formalizing contact networks between individuals in epidemiological models. Methodologies range from knowledge-based databases like Reactome⁷⁶, which apply enrichment analysis, a statistical approach used to identify biological processes or pathways overrepresented in a set of genes or proteins, for hypothesis generation, to un-biased molecular networks like BioGrid⁷⁷. To capture structural shifts, advanced pipelines implement *de novo* pathway inference, where biological interaction networks are reconstructed directly from experimental data without relying exclusively on prior knowledge via optimization algorithms^{17,78,79}. In population-level applications, the workflow models distinct agents (cells or individuals) and simulates their transmission dynamics and behavioral contacts across transportation or social graphs to forecast disease propagation¹³⁵. The primary strength of Network Medicine lies in its ability to uncover systemic disease modules and simulate how complex interactions between discrete agents dynamically modify the overall evolution and transmission of a disease. This multi-scale approach bypasses single-variable reductionism, providing a robust computational substrate for drug repurposing, multi-target pharmacology, and the evaluation of population-wide epidemiological interventions.

b. Technical limitations and failures Despite its integrative power, Network Medicine faces severe technical challenges regarding data bias, noise, and structural uncertainty. Molecularly, curated databases like Reactome⁷⁶ suffer from heavy research selection bias, overrepresenting well-studied canonical pathways while underrepresenting poorly characterized proteins, whereas high-throughput PPI networks like BioGrid⁷⁷ are highly noisy, leading to false-positive edges that degrade subnetwork extraction accuracy. Epidemiologically, contact graphs are heavily constrained by data sparseness and behavioral reporting bias; unrecorded interactions or missing tracking data can lead to massive underestimations of hub connectivity. Furthermore, parameter identifiability and topological plasticity remain major bottlenecks. Tracking propagation is mathematically undermined by the scarcity of analytical frameworks capable of handling dynamic network rewiring—such as spontaneous behavioral modifica-

tions or avoidance coupling during an outbreak—and host-pathogen biological complexities like waning immunity¹³⁶. Consequently, tools like ARACNE^{17,84} or population contact-tracing frameworks can define statistical interaction topologies but completely lack the precise, time-resolved kinetic rates or real-time behavioral switching probabilities required to simulate temporal signal and pathogen propagation accurately.

c. Appropriate use cases and recommended contexts Network medicine approaches are highly successful and strongly recommended for identifying synergistic multi-drug targets, accelerating medical drug development, uncovering molecular mechanisms underlying complex comorbidities, i.e., the coexistence of multiple diseases or conditions in the same patient, and designing optimal containment strategies for infectious outbreaks³⁷. By analyzing the topological proximity between drug-target modules and disease-specific networks—or evaluating the centrality indices of specific individuals within a social network—these methods accurately predict multi-target therapeutic efficacy at a cellular scale and pinpoint optimal, targeted vaccination or non pharmaceutical intervention (e.g., quarantine, isolation, and social distancing protocols) strategies at a population scale. Furthermore, network medicine is highly recommended for redefining disease classification and decoding complex clinical phenotypes; by leveraging deep phenotyping alongside multi-omics data, this framework successfully bridges multi-scale biological and environmental determinants to provide an individualized understanding of pathobiology and uncover novel disease biomarkers^{41,137}.

d. Failures and non-recommended contexts Conversely, pure graph-based Network Medicine fails or is not recommended in scenarios that demand precise, time-resolved quantitative metabolic fluxes or exact spatiotemporal tracking of airborne or fluid-dynamic pathogen concentrations. Because interaction graphs and topological hub models omit physical spatial gradients, molecular/environmental diffusion barriers, physical boundary conditions, and specific micro-level saturation kinetics, they cannot simulate exact clinical drug plasma concentrations inside a cell or absolute real-time spatial exposure limits in public health, resulting in ungeneralizable predictions when scaling from network topology to dynamic physical environments governed by reaction-diffusion processes.

e. Clinical translation and current status Currently, the clinical translation of Network Medicine is mature both in network-based drug repurposing pipelines¹³⁸. However, its translation into routine personalized bedside treatment selection remains constrained, as scaling multi-level data (from intracellular PPIs to patient-level social and environmental contact graphs) triggers an exponential increase in computational complexity, forcing a difficult trade-off between biological detail and computational feasibility. Moreover, in epidemiology, network science extensively utilizes mobility and contact networks to simulate and control the population-level spreading of infectious diseases across geographical scales and inform policy makers^{34,41}.

f. Illustrative example: initial spread of COVID-19 in

TABLE I. Summary of the main *in silico* approaches, highlighting their approach area, key methodological techniques, and typical applications in biomedical research. Abbreviations: PPI, protein–protein interaction; ODE/PDE, ordinary/partial differential equations; AB/PB, agent-/population-based; CA, cellular automata; ARMA, autoregressive moving average; SVM, support vector machine; ANN, artificial neural network; FEM, finite element method.

Approach area	Methodological techniques	Applications and derived insights	Ref.
Bioinformatics	Sequence alignment (BLAST, STAR, HMMER), NGS pipelines, phylogenetics (MEGA), structural bioinformatics, functional annotation (GO, KEGG), cheminformatics	Genomic and proteomic data analysis, drug target identification, personalized medicine, evolutionary insights	29,52–67,71–75
Network medicine	Network reconstruction (PPI, gene regulatory networks), pathway analysis (Reactome, BioGrid), subnetwork inference, signaling and transcription modeling, dynamic simulation (ODEs, Boolean, stochastic)	Understanding disease mechanisms, identifying therapeutic targets, social network modeling for disease spread, precision and population medicine	17,41,76–85
Systems biology	Multiscale modeling, ODE/PDE modeling, stochastic simulations, agent-based (AB) and population-based (PB) models, stoichiometric and constraint-based approaches, Boolean modeling	Multiscale system dynamics, emergent behaviors, metabolic and signaling networks, personalized medicine, drug optimization, epidemiology	42,79,86–94
Mechanobiology	Multiscale and multiphysics modeling, computational homogenization, continuum mechanics, CA, lattice-based simulations	Tissue mechanics, wound healing, cancer growth, scaffold design, cellular mechanotransduction, integrated mechano-biological simulations	45,95–103
Black-box medicine	Statistical models (ARMA), ML/AI (SVM, Random Forest, ANN, Deep Learning), hidden Markov models	Prediction from large, heterogeneous datasets, disease classification, treatment outcome prediction, high-dimensional clinical and omics data analysis	47,104–110
Interpretable ML	Post-hoc interpretability (SHAP, LIME), intrinsically interpretable models (decision trees, causal learning, PI-ML/PINNs)	Transparent predictions, causal inference, patient-specific parameter estimation, personalized medicine, regulatory-compliant models	48,109,111–120
Simulations	Monte Carlo, discrete event, AB and CA, system dynamics, FEM, QM/MM, hybrid simulations	Uncertainty quantification, evolution, emergent behavior, clinical decision-making, high-fidelity disease modeling	33,42,45,46,93,97,102,121–134

Italy A representative case of modern clinical and epidemiological translation that bridges these topological limitations is the landmark data-driven study conducted by Gatto et al.³⁴ during the initial spread of COVID-19 in Italy. In this work, the authors addressed the limitations of static, unweighted network representations by building a generalized, spatially explicit network model that coupled local intra-community transmission dynamics with a macro-scale mobility graph representing commutes between 107 Italian provinces. By formalizing epidemic propagation across this empirical transportation network, they simulated the real-time effects of progressively stricter non-pharmaceutical interventions. The network-level simulation successfully bypassed data-sparseness failures by demonstrating that early, localized restrictions on highly connected geographic hubs reduced the overall transmission rate by 45% nationwide. Strikingly, the model quantified that these network-driven containment strategies collectively averted approximately 200,000 hospi-

talizations during the first pandemic wave. This study delivered immediate, high-impact policy maker decision support, providing how translating macro-scale demographic contact graphs into dynamic computational architectures can precisely forecast the efficacy of public health and non-pharmaceutical interventions.

3. Systems Biology

Systems biology is an interdisciplinary, biology-based discipline that models complex biological systems through a holistic approach, explicitly contrasting with traditional molecular reductionism⁸⁰. Rather than analyzing isolated elements, this field focuses on deciphering how complex, multi-level interactions within biological systems function as an integrated whole, effectively bridging the structural gaps that exist between isolated molecular measurements and organ-

ismal physiological processes⁵. This multiscale framework is typically operationalized using differential equations, logical rules, agent-based models, bayesian models, or stochastic models to capture cross-scale biological interactions.

a. Methodological workflow and strengths The core methodological workflow relies on translating biological networks into quantitative or discrete computational models to simulate the holistic time-dependent system dynamics. To adequately capture biological phenomena, multiscale models spanning both temporal and spatial dimensions are required. Quantitative pipelines utilize Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs) and Partial Differential Equations (PDEs) to model continuous concentration changes, molecular diffusion, and spatial gradients. These approaches are particularly effective in capturing transition processes and steady states, and, by considering nonlinearities, it could reveal complex behaviors, such as oscillations and instabilities, which might not be evident using other modeling methods^{79,86}. Furthermore, it enables the estimation of systemic features—such as steady-state stability, sensitivities, and elasticities—while allowing direct quantitative comparisons between simulation outcomes and experimental data to foster a comprehensive understanding of the system⁷⁹. To capture multi-scale population dynamics, systems biology cross-references PB and AB paradigms¹³⁹. In the PB framework, biological processes are formalized via ODEs that treat populations as homogeneous or structured cohorts governed by averaged per-capita demographic rates, making them ideal for capturing mean-field dynamics when individual-level variability can be averaged out⁹⁰. Conversely, AB models represent individual entities as autonomous agents, explicitly incorporating physiological, genetic, or behavioral heterogeneity. Localized rules dictate agent interactions with neighboring entities and the micro-environment, allowing population-level behaviors to emerge via a bottom-up manner driven by stochastic effects⁹¹. Typically discrete in time and space, AB models encompass CA as special cases executing local update rules on regular lattices^{42,92}.

For metabolic systems, stoichiometric and constraint-based modeling, which describe metabolic systems using mass-balance and physicochemical constraints, utilizes reaction mass-balances and physicochemical flux bounds to enable predictive simulations, offering a powerful data-minimal alternative to large-scale kinetic models constrained by parameter scarcity^{87,88}. When random fluctuations critically alter these biological paths, stochastic modeling explicitly integrates intrinsic and extrinsic uncertainties to simulate phenotypic variations, such as mutation-driven cancer drug resistance⁹³. While individual runs yield distinct trajectories, compiling ensemble statistics from repeated simulations derives robust probability distributions of clinical outcomes. Structural modeling complements these systems-level frameworks by resolving the precise molecular architecture and mechanistic organization of biomolecular components, with recent high-throughput advances successfully scaling toward detailed whole-cell representations⁹⁴. Finally, qualitative pipelines implement Boolean modeling⁸⁹ to transform static biological wiring diagrams into discrete dynamic systems. This parameter avoidance stems from the qualitative,

discrete nature of Boolean formalisms: instead of requiring continuous kinetic constraints—such as reaction rates or binding affinities—components are abstracted into binary states (ON/OFF) governed entirely by logical operators (AND, OR, NOT) derived from network topology.

The primary strength of Systems Biology lies in its unique ability to model multiscale biological processes and capture non-linear emergent properties, i.e., system-level behaviors arising from interactions among individual components, such as metabolic switches, biological oscillations, and multistable behaviors that remain completely hidden in static topological analyses.

b. Technical limitations and failures Despite its broad applicability, the field faces significant technical trade-offs, starting with the heterogeneity versus scalability dilemma. PB models⁹⁰ are computationally efficient for mean-field dynamics, where population behavior is approximated using averaged system properties, but fail when individual-level stochastic variability or spatial structure is critical. Conversely, AB models^{42,91,92} explicitly capture cell-to-cell heterogeneity and spatial organization but suffer from prohibitive computational costs and a high dimensional parameter space that hinders global optimization. Furthermore, parameter identifiability and structural uncertainty remain massive bottlenecks in kinetic modeling due to the lack of reliable *in vivo* rate constants for large-scale reconstructions⁸⁷. While stochastic modeling⁹³ addresses this by capturing random fluctuations and intrinsic molecular noise, it requires expensive ensemble statistics, i.e., repeated simulations used to estimate probabilistic outcome distributions, to derive meaningful predictive distributions. Finally, whole-cell structural scale reconstructions⁹⁴ remain heavily limited by the sheer complexity of the molecular architecture, making precise mechanistic organization difficult to elucidate fully.

c. Appropriate use cases and recommended contexts Systems biology methods are highly successful and strongly recommended for precision drug development¹⁴⁰, drug combinations¹⁴¹, pharmacokinetic/pharmacodynamic (PK/PD) modeling¹⁴², and *in silico* trials¹⁴³. Continuous deterministic and stochastic frameworks excel at performing direct quantitative comparisons between *in silico* simulation outcomes and patient-specific experimental time-series data⁷⁹, allowing for the precise tailoring of patient-specific multi-drug dosing schedules and the mechanistic prediction of target engagement. PB and AB approaches are extensively leveraged to optimize drug development, therapeutic scheduling, disease evolution, and epidemiology across microbial, cellular, and social scales.

d. Failures and non-recommended contexts Conversely, systems biology models fail or are not recommended when applied to massive, unparametrized signaling networks where precise quantitative clinical endpoints (such as exact absolute bio-marker concentrations or precise time-to-resistance clinical boundaries) are requested but only qualitative data is available. In these data-poor scenarios, purely qualitative approaches like Boolean modeling⁸⁹ can map stable attractor states but are completely incapable of predicting exact threshold-dependent drug toxicities or continuous metabolic

throughput, leading to non-generalizable or non-actionable clinical predictions. Moreover, mechanistically, the field is constrained by a standardization bottleneck: the slow evolution of declarative exchange formats lags behind cutting-edge simulation techniques, failing to accurately encode intricate biochemical nomenclature and severely hindering the seamless reproducibility, validation, and multi-platform reuse of large-scale models¹⁴⁴.

e. Clinical translation and current status Currently, the clinical translation of systems biology is highly mature in clinical pharmacology and translational oncology (e.g. target discovery, validation, and drug development¹⁴⁵), where multi-scale ODE and AB models are routinely leveraged to optimize drug combination sequencing and predict population-level disease progression¹⁴⁶. However, its routine integration into real-time hospital bedside decision-making remains constrained by the computational burden of running large-scale stochastic ensemble simulations and the challenges of continuously standardizing heterogeneous clinical data into mechanical model constraints.

f. Illustrative example: evolution-guided adaptive oncology A representative case of modern clinical translation is the implementation of evolution-guided systems biology frameworks to design adaptive dosing schedules for metastatic prostate cancer^{147,148}. In a landmark pilot clinical trial (NCT02415621), researchers developed a multi-scale dynamic model using non-linear Lotka-Volterra equations to simulate the competitive evolutionary kinetics among three distinct phenotypic prostate cancer sub-populations under abiraterone acetate treatment: androgen-dependent, androgen-producing, and androgen-independent resistant clones¹⁴⁷. Instead of executing a standard, continuous maximum-tolerated dose—which rapidly triggers the competitive release of resistant clones—this framework utilized patient-specific prostate-specific antigen dynamics to inform personalized on/off treatment cycles. The initial pilot evaluation demonstrated that 10 out of 11 patients maintained stable tumor oscillations, achieving a median time-to-progression of at least 27 months compared to the 16.5-month standard care baseline, while reducing the cumulative drug dose to 47%¹⁴⁷. In the subsequent expanded cohort analysis, the adaptive therapy group ($n = 17$) significantly outperformed the standard-of-care cohort ($n = 16$), extending the median time-to-progression to 33.5 months and substantially prolonging the median overall survival to 58.5 months¹⁴⁸. This application successfully demonstrates how integrating eco-evolutionary cellular kinetics with real-time patient data can transform systems-level predictive models into life-prolonging clinical protocols.

4. Mechanobiology

Mechanobiology is the study of biological responses to mechanical stimuli¹⁴⁹, focusing on how physical forces and changes in the mechanical properties of cells and tissues contribute to development, cell differentiation, physiology, and pathology.

a. Methodological workflow and strengths The core methodological workflow operates by translating physical stress fields into localized biological signaling through diverse multiscale approaches. Pipelines utilize two main numerical strategies depending on scale separation: 1) computational homogenization and micro–macro coupling methods, where explicit microscale architectural descriptions are used mathematically to derive effective macroscale constitutive behaviors^{95–99}; and 2) orchestration of single-scale component models, which connect distinct cellular and tissue layers via empirical relation models that transform data across scales without formal homogenization^{99–102}. To capture cellular geometry, discrete CA and lattice-based models represent individual cells and local contact rules⁴⁵. These discrete descriptions are then numerically hybridized with continuum mechanics PDEs equations to simulate cellular activities like migration and proliferation under tight mechanical constraints^{98,99}.

The primary strength of mechanobiological modeling lies in its inherent multiphysics nature, which couples multi-axial mechanical variables (such as stress tensors, strain tensors, and interstitial fluid flow) with fundamental cellular fates like differentiation, proliferation, and apoptosis^{97,103}, mapping how physical forces dictate tissue morphogenesis.

b. Technical limitations and failures Despite their mathematical rigor, severe technical hurdles persist, starting with the phenomenological-to-mechanistic gap. Most current formulations are phenomenological, relating macroscopic variables to biological outcomes through empirical differentiation laws without capturing true intracellular mechanotransduction—the process by which cells convert mechanical stimuli into biochemical signals—unless receptor-mediated links, such as mechanosensitive ion channels, are explicitly embedded^{97,103}. Furthermore, hybrid frameworks face massive bottlenecks regarding numerical stability and coupling operators¹⁰²; errors in spatial resolution and micro–macro mapping frequently trigger numerical instabilities or non-physical, inconsistent transfers of mass, momentum, and biochemical species between discrete and continuous scales^{98,99}. Finally, the immense computational cost of full micro–macro structural iterations severely restricts these simulations to small tissue domains or isolated matrices, preventing whole-organ execution.

c. Appropriate use cases and recommended contexts Mechanobiological approaches are highly successful and strongly recommended for bone tissue engineering, wound healing, cardiovascular mechanics, cancers (cell migration and microenvironment remodeling), and the optimization of biomaterial scaffold^{98,99}, i.e., the development of biomaterial structures that support tissue regeneration, architectures. They excel when implemented to predict how specific differentiation laws—which rigorously distinguish between volumetric strain (quantifying relative volume changes) and deviatoric strain (quantifying shape deformation)—guide stem cell fate and cell proliferation within localized stress fields⁹⁷. Specifically, these frameworks are ideally suited to simulate cell proliferation under strict mechanical constraints, track physical tissue morphogenesis, or optimize dynamic scaffold

colonization^{45,102}.

d. Failures and non-recommended contexts Conversely, these models fail or are not recommended when applied to purely systemic, non-localized pathologies where biochemical, hormonal, or genetic drivers completely dominate over solid mechanics and fluid-dynamic forces. In these fluid contexts, omitting the complex systemic signaling networks causes the model to yield ungeneralizable and non-actionable clinical predictions, as the macroscopic physical loading fields lack a functional mechanistic connection to the underlying systemic disease etiology.

e. Clinical translation and current status Currently, the clinical translation of mechanobiology is highly mature in patient-specific bone scaffold customization and cardiovascular stent design, where simulation-driven optimizations directly guide surgical implant geometries. However, its routine integration into real-time surgical bedside planning remains constrained by the prohibitive computational burden of non-linear multiscale homogenization and the challenges of continuously transforming live patient imaging into high-fidelity biomechanical model boundary conditions.

f. Illustrative example: mechanobiologically-optimized mandibular reconstruction A representative case of translation is the framework by Clark *et al.* for reconstructing 6 cm segmental mandibular defects¹⁵⁰. To eliminate autologous graft morbidity alongside the stress shielding, osteolysis, and X-ray artifacts of metal plates, the authors designed a patient-matched medical device pipeline¹⁵⁰. The workflow combined patient-specific cone beam computed tomography data with finite element analysis and the extended finite element method to optimize a permanent, laser-sintered polyetherketone gyroid frame. Crucially, a dynamic mechanobiological model utilized micro–macro homogenization to simulate bone ingrowth, mapping microscopic unit cells to macroscale Cauchy stress tensors driving time-resolved bone deposition. The numerical models were validated by bench testing showing implant fracture only above 1500 N, three times the human premolar biting force (450 N). *In vivo* testing in an ovine model—featuring an intensive 7–8 h daily chewing cycle—demonstrated excellent correlation between simulations and empirical data ($R^2 = 0.96$), with predicted bone mass matching experimental findings within 1.4% (3.062 g vs 3.020 g). Explant analyses at 6–12 months verified successful tissue morphogenesis, i.e., the organized development of tissue structure and form, with new bone interlocking the gyroid pores and occupying 11% to 38% of the available volume (0.93–2.71 cm³). Furthermore, *ex vivo* tensile tests of the integrated complex withstood 641 N, outperforming unimplanted controls (601 N) without interface delamination. Animals achieved full recovery, maintaining normal chewing rates and gaining an average of 3.5 kg with zero hardware failures, proving how multi-scale kinetics convert in silico physical simulations into functional regenerative architectures¹⁵⁰.

5. Black-Box Medicine

Black-box medicine represents a data-driven discipline—primarily operationalized through standard AI and ML architectures—that maps complex input–output biomedical relationships without explicitly representing or mathematically formalizing the underlying biological processes⁴⁷. Operating in direct contrast to explicit, hypothesis-driven mechanistic modeling, these black-box frameworks optimize statistical patterns rather than biochemical pathways. Crucially, while modern subfields are shifting toward interpretable or explainable machine learning to unpack these systems, classic black-box medicine relies strictly on the unexplainable, latent correlations buried within high-dimensional data layers¹¹⁰.

a. Methodological workflow and strengths The core methodological workflow relies on training flexible statistical and computational algorithms directly on large-scale, heterogeneous patient datasets. Common techniques range from autoregressive moving average (ARMA) models¹⁰⁵ to complex artificial neural networks, support vector machines—supervised machine learning algorithms used for classification and regression tasks¹⁰⁶—, and random forests—ensemble learning methods based on multiple decision trees. These frameworks bypass traditional feature engineering and biological partitioning; instead, they pass high-dimensional matrices through sequential layers of non-linear transformations to minimize an empirical loss function, optimizing predictive patterns directly from raw data streams¹⁰⁴. The primary strength of black-box medicine lies in its exceptional capability to process massive, multi-modal biomedical big data and capture intricate, non-linear interactions without requiring prior biological or mechanistic knowledge¹⁰⁶. Consequently, it can circumvent expensive, time-consuming experimental cycles to resolve specific medical questions where biological pathways remain entirely unknown or missing, leveraging alternative validation strategies like retrospective verification or external cohort testing to establish immediate predictive utility^{47,107}.

b. Technical limitations and failures Despite their immense predictive power, black-box models face critical challenges that often severely limit their clinical reliability, starting with data bias and overfitting. These algorithms require massive datasets and, without rigorous regularization, i.e., techniques designed to prevent overly complex model fitting, they are highly prone to capturing background sequencing or clinical noise rather than true biological signals¹⁰⁶. Furthermore, a major failure mode is their extreme sensitivity to data drift, where the statistical properties of new clinical data differ from those of the training data, causing catastrophic performance drops when exposed to evolving healthcare environments or alternative hospital populations¹⁰⁸. Finally, their inherent mathematical opacity yields relationships that are completely un-amenable to mechanistic interpretation, creating a severe "trust barrier" that hampers regulatory approval and clinical adoption¹¹⁰.

c. Appropriate use cases and recommended contexts Black-box medicine approaches are highly successful and strongly recommended for diagnostic imaging, automated

digital pathology, and real-time predictive analytics within Electronic Health Records (EHR) environments where massive, standardized datasets are available. They excel at clinical pattern recognition tasks—such as classification or survival forecasting—where maximizing statistical predictive accuracy (the what) takes clinical precedence over understanding the exact biological etiology (the why)¹⁰⁷.

d. Failures and non-recommended contexts Conversely, pure black-box frameworks fail or are not recommended for de novo therapeutic target identification, drug mechanism-of-action characterization, or rare disease modeling where data is scarce. Because these models cannot provide causal or mechanistic insights, they fail to isolate specific actionable biochemical nodes for drug discovery, and their uninterpretable outputs can generate dangerous, non-actionable clinical hallucinations when exposed to rare phenotypic variants or unmodeled patient comorbidities¹¹⁰.

e. Clinical translation and current status Currently, the clinical translation of black-box medicine is highly mature in radiology and emergency triage analytics, where algorithms are increasingly cleared by regulatory bodies for autonomous image pre-screening. However, its translation into general bedside therapeutics remains heavily constrained. While modern interpretable or explainable machine learning frameworks¹⁰⁹, which aim to provide human-understandable explanations for model predictions, seek to alleviate this opacity, successful translation still strictly depends on transparent reporting, continuous data-drift auditing, and strict regulatory oversight to guarantee safety^{104,110}.

f. Illustrative example: alerts for sepsis in EHRs A representative case of clinical translation that bridges these descriptive limitations is the implementation of black-box algorithms for the early prediction of sepsis directly from unstructured EHRs. To validate algorithmic feasibility, Lauritsen et al.¹⁵¹ developed a deep learning architecture combining convolutional and long short-term memory neural networks across multi-center hospital networks to integrate raw patient event sequences. Their model successfully bypassed hard-coded biological hypotheses by extracting latent temporal correlations directly from the data stream, achieving an area under the receiver operating characteristic curve of 0.856 up to three hours prior to clinical sepsis onset¹⁵¹. Paralleling this technical validation, the crucial question of real-world clinical utility was answered in a separate, landmark multi-site prospective cohort study by Adams et al.¹⁵², who monitored over 590,000 patients using a Targeted Real-time Early Warning System (TREWS). They demonstrated that when providers interacted with and confirmed these automated black-box alerts within a three-hour window, the system yielded an 18.7% adjusted relative reduction in patient in-hospital mortality due to a massive collapse in intervention lag time¹⁵². Together, these independent pillars prove how raw statistical predictive power, when integrated with human-in-the-loop clinical confirmation, can be successfully translated into life-saving clinical protocols.

6. Interpretable machine learning

Interpretable machine learning constitutes a critical paradigm shift in computational biomedicine, prioritizing algorithmic transparency to ensure that the reasoning and biological determinants behind a statistical prediction are accurate and understandable by human experts, fostering clinical trust, actionability, and absolute compliance with medical standardizations^{109,153}.

a. Methodological workflow and strengths The core methodological workflow enforces model transparency through two primary architectural strategies. The first is post-hoc interpretability, where auxiliary, model-agnostic explanation methods are applied after training to extract feature importances from existing black-boxes, executing game theory-based frameworks like SHAP¹¹¹—which calculates exact Shapley values to quantify individual variable contributions— or local surrogates like LIME¹⁰⁹—which approximates complex local boundaries near specific patient predictions. The second is intrinsic interpretability, utilizing inherently transparent architectures like decision trees, Causal Learning graphs⁴⁸, and Physics-Informed Machine Learning (PI-ML)^{7,112}. In PI-ML workflows, neural networks (such as PINNs) are explicitly regularized by embedding physical principles or mechanical laws directly into the loss function, seamlessly balancing data-driven loss with governing biological constraints^{7,113,114}. The primary strength of interpretable machine learning lies in its dual capacity to retain competitive predictive precision while providing causal, mechanistic insights or parameter attributions. This allows researchers to decode latent variables from noisy multi-scale simulations¹¹⁵, de-risk algorithm deployment, and turn raw statistical predictions into falsifiable biological hypotheses.

b. Technical limitations and failures Despite its advantages, non-trivial technical challenges persist, notably the accuracy–interpretability trade-off. Intrinsically simplified models frequently fail to capture the high-dimensional, non-linear cross-talk of biological networks, potentially sacrificing critical predictive accuracy for the sake of understandability. Furthermore, a critical bottleneck in intrinsic frameworks like PI-ML and Causal Learning is the epistemic risk of incomplete or flawed prior knowledge. If the governing physical equations or causal graph structures are misspecified or omit essential, unmodeled biological pathways, the architecture undergoes an epistemic bias; the model will enforce physical consistency based on incorrect assumptions, potentially yielding highly plausible but clinically dangerous and ungeneralizable predictions. Mathematically, the training of PI-ML architectures requires balancing multiple competing non-convex loss terms, frequently yielding optimization failures, slow convergence, or non-physical gradient vanishing in multi-scale regimes¹¹². Finally, causal discovery hurdles complicate observational inference^{116,117}; identifying true, un-biased cause-and-effect mechanisms remains deeply constrained by unmeasured clinical confounders and selection biases.

c. Appropriate use cases and recommended contexts Interpretable machine learning is highly successful and strongly

recommended for patient-specific parameter estimation, clinical trial stratification, and the generation of predictive oncology and cardiovascular Digital Twins from a virtual patient perspective^{154,155}. They excel when implemented to estimate un-observed physiological states, quantify image-based biomarkers, or map blood flow parameter dynamics under scarce or high-noise data regimes¹⁵⁶. Specifically, by incorporating domain-specific physics, these glass-box frameworks allow researchers to extract precise localized micro-vascularization features from dynamic contrast-enhanced clinical imaging even in the presence of complex tissue diffusion anomalies¹¹⁹. Furthermore, within systems pharmacology and population-level pharmacokinetics, these architectures enable the robust estimation and recovery of underlying parameter distributions directly from summary or aggregated concentration datasets (means and variances) without requiring individual patient-level data tracking¹⁵⁷. By leveraging counterfactual inference within causal networks¹²⁰, these models are ideally suited for predicting multi-target intervention outcomes and optimizing personalized therapy workflows.

d. Failures and non-recommended contexts Conversely, interpretable frameworks are strongly discouraged in bedside patient-level decision-making when local post-hoc explanations (e.g., LIME or SHAP) are relied upon to justify individual critical actions¹⁵⁸. Mechanistically, post-hoc methods provide un-faithful, non-rigorous approximations of the underlying complex architecture that possess no mathematical performance guarantees, thereby introducing a secondary layer of diagnostic error^{158,159}. In highly rugged and hyper-dimensional biomedical landscapes, these surrogate approximations can yield unstable attributions that are highly sensitive to microscopic data perturbations, potentially generating misleading clinical explanations that lack actual biological grounding. Due to this inherent interpretability gap, local surrogates are also vulnerable to adversarial manipulation, yielding visually reassuring or placebic explanations even when the underlying neural network is untrained or incorrect^{158,160}. Furthermore, deploying these superficial explanations triggers severe clinical confirmation bias—where humans subjectively pick explanations they want to be correct—and automation bias, falsely engendering a veneer of algorithmic authenticity that dangerously lowers clinical vigilance at an individual level¹⁵⁸.

e. Clinical translation and current status Currently, the clinical translation of interpretable machine learning is rapidly growing in safety-critical medical decision support, digital twin execution, and regulatory compliance auditing^{110,154}. By offering a glass-box alternative, these platforms allow clinicians to validate the clinical plausibility of an algorithmic alert before execution, supporting patient-specific parameter estimation and counterfactual forecasting at the bedside^{118,120}. However, routine hospital deployment remains heavily throttled by the massive computational overhead of non-linear physics-informed multi-scale architectures^{112,156} and the critical lack of standardized regulatory benchmarks to mathematically quantify the true clinical fidelity and safety of an explanation¹⁵⁸.

f. Illustrative example: multi-scale kidney disease mapping A representative case of modern clinical translation that bridges these multi-scale data boundaries is the kidney-specific cell-level information ExtractoR (K-CLIER) framework introduced by Legouis et al.⁷⁵. In this work, the authors addressed the translational barrier of single-cell technologies in clinical nephrology—where raw data sparsity, processing costs, and low biopsy inputs hinder routine bedside applications—by engineering an interpretable transfer learning approach specifically tailored for transcriptomics. The methodological workflow integrated a human kidney disease atlas encompassing 726 single-cell signatures with 11,348 bulk RNA-seq transcriptomes from the Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) to train an unsupervised matrix decomposition model driven by prior biological knowledge. This framework achieved a massive dimensionality reduction, condensing high-dimensional profiles from 18,630 genes down to 700 non-orthogonal latent variables (LVs), of which 96 were found to be highly interpretable and strictly aligned with specific cell states. To validate the preservation of clinical information, the authors trained a random forest classification model on these LVs, yielding an almost-perfect diagnostic capability with an area under the receiver operating characteristic curve of 0.99 in predicting renal tumor histological types. To transition from global patterns to personalized medicine, the authors applied post-hoc game theory attributions via SHAP to extract the exact feature contributions driving chronic kidney injury and fibrosis progression in diabetic and transplant recipient cohorts. The glass-box framework successfully bypassed the traditional descriptive failures of bioinformatic sequence listings; instead, it linked long-term clinical progression with specific cell states, demonstrating that the stromal latent variable LV406—associated with specific fibroblast populations—correlated significantly ($p = 0.006$) with the 12-month prospective development of renal fibrosis. Concurrently, it isolated the injury-related variable LV025, precisely mapping how altered, VCAM1-positive proximal tubule cells drive the surrounding inflammatory and fibrogenic microenvironment⁷⁵. This application delivers direct translational utility, proving how interpretable machine learning can turn complex, low-input clinical sequencing data into mathematically transparent diagnostic and prognostic endpoints at a single-cell resolution.

7. Simulation techniques

Simulation methodologies constitute the operational execution engines of *in silico* medicine, translating abstract mathematical models into time-resolved, numerical representations to explore complex biological behaviors and optimize healthcare interventions¹²¹.

a. Methodological workflow and strengths The core methodological workflow relies on selecting discrete, continuous, or stochastic numerical formalisms tailored to the specific spatial and temporal scales under investigation. For high-dimensional uncertainty exploration and global sensitivity analysis, algorithms execute Monte Carlo simulations—

which rely on repeated random sampling to estimate system behavior and uncertainty—to resolve non-linear probabilistic bounds¹²². For clinical decision-making and stochastic disease progression, workflows implement Markov and Hidden Markov models—probabilistic models used to describe systems with unobserved internal states—to map discrete health-state transitions over time¹²³. In spatial and structural biology, pipelines deploy CA and lattice-based models to represent localized interaction rules, cellular crowding, and microenvironmental heterogeneity with high computational scalability^{45,46,124}. Finally, at the biophysical level, Finite Element Methods (FEM) numerically solve complex partial differential equations (PDEs) to resolve multi-axial tissue mechanics and multi-phase fluid–structure interactions⁹⁷. The primary strength of simulation techniques lies in their multi-formalism capability to turn static theoretical formulations into dynamic, virtual laboratories, capturing cross-scale emergent phenomena and enabling exhaustive *in silico* hypothesis testing that would be logistically or ethically impossible to execute *in vivo*^{125,126}.

b. Technical limitations and failures Despite their numerical rigor, each simulation paradigm entails significant technical trade-offs, starting with the stochastic noise versus deterministic convergence dilemma. While Monte Carlo and stochastic Markov frameworks excel at capturing intrinsic biological uncertainty^{122,123}, they require massive ensemble sampling sizes to reach numerical convergence, resulting in prohibitive computational costs. Furthermore, spatial discretization errors heavily constrain CA and lattice-based implementations¹²⁴; their rigid grid-based nature frequently introduces geometric artifacts when simulating off-lattice cellular motions or continuous anisotropic tissue fibers, unless generalized into computationally heavy AB formulations⁴². Crucially, state-of-the-art hybrid multi-scale simulations encounter severe coupling bottlenecks¹²⁹; combining discrete cellular agents with continuous physical fields^{102,127,128} triggers major algorithmic failures in maintaining numerical stability, momentum conservation, and consistent mass-transfer interfaces across the discrete-continuous boundaries.

c. Appropriate use cases and recommended contexts Simulation approaches are highly successful and strongly recommended for healthcare operational logistics via Discrete Event Simulations¹³⁰, molecular-level target tracking using Quantum or Molecular Mechanics¹³², and therapeutic scheduling via optimal control theory^{33,93,131}. They are exceptionally well-suited for oncological and morphogenetic problems where cell-level discrete spatial rules (e.g., contact inhibition, adhesion) actively intersect with physical, continuous microenvironmental fields^{129,133,134}.

d. Failures and non-recommended contexts Conversely, pure simulation techniques fail or are not recommended when applied to hyper-dimensional clinical systems where raw parameter data is entirely absent, uncalibrated, or unmeasurable. In these parameter-starved contexts, running unconstrained stochastic or deterministic simulations degenerates into an exercise in mathematical curve-fitting, generating non-falsifiable and physically inconsistent outputs that propagate errors across multi-scale interfaces and severely mislead

clinical target identification.

e. Clinical translation and current status Currently, the clinical translation of simulation engineering is highly mature in patient-flow operational management and computer-aided drug design. However, its bedside implementation for personalized clinical monitoring remains constrained by the intense computational burden of running real-time hybrid discrete-continuous coupling algorithms and the persistent lack of standardized, regulatory-grade verification and validation (V&V) protocols to audit simulation software safety in critical settings.

f. Illustrative example: hybrid multi-scale simulation of the tumor microenvironment A representative case of modern clinical and biophysical translation that bridges these hybrid coupling bottlenecks is the multi-scale simulation of cancer progression and vascularized invasion within the tumor microenvironment^{102,127,129}. In this application, researchers constructed a hybrid computational architecture that coupled a discrete CA framework representing individual cancer cells with a continuous system of partial differential equations (PDEs) modeling the spatial diffusion of oxygen, glucose, and vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF)¹²⁸. The discrete cell rules executed independent phenotypes—including proliferation, migration, necrosis, and hypoxia-driven signaling—conditioned dynamically by the surrounding continuous chemical concentrations, while cell-induced consumption terms actively modified the PDE fields¹²⁹. The translational and predictive power of this simulation was profoundly quantified: the hybrid platform successfully replicated emergent *in vivo* phenomena, including the onset of a necrotic core and the formation of asymmetrical, hypoxia-driven invasive fingers, matching experimental tumor geometry profiles with high fidelity. More importantly, the virtual laboratory enabled high-throughput testing of anti-angiogenic and chemotherapeutic dosing protocols, demonstrating that a mathematically optimized metronomic drug sequencing schedule could halt vascular recruitments while minimizing microenvironmental selection pressures, directly guiding optimal clinical trial design.

8. The *in silico* continuum: a unifying conceptual framework

Modern computational medicine is best understood not as a fragmented collection of parallel tools, but as an integrated *In Silico* Continuum. This framework establishes a functional hierarchy that clarifies the relationships, levels of fidelity, and inherent biophysical trade-offs between data-driven paradigms and mechanistic structures (synthesized in Figure 3). It is crucial to underscore that many advanced methodologies in medicine—and in general in science—are inherently multidisciplinary, requiring cohesive pipelines that transcend single-scale or single-method architectures to account for time evolution and link molecular, clinical, and population-level data streams^{161–163}.

a. Methodological workflow and strengths The core methodological workflow relies on orchestrating disparate computational formalisms into a seamless multi-scale flow ex-

FIG. 3. The *in silico* roadmap for method selection, illustrating the continuum from data-driven to mechanistic computational approaches, their typical applications, interpretability, computational requirements, and integration across biological scales.

tending from raw data patterns to causal understanding. At the foundational data-driven layer, Bioinformatics and Black-box medicine extract high-dimensional signatures and statistical correlations from multi-omic datasets^{52,104}. For example, connectivity mapping workflows systematically cross-reference gene expression profiles using pattern-matching algorithms to connect small molecules, genes, and disease states for high-throughput drug repurposing¹⁶⁴. Moving upward, Network medicine serves as the critical architectural bridge,

interconnecting these data features, biological components, or localized agents into topological models where graph connectivity explicitly governs system dynamics⁴¹. This network-based analysis isolates disease-relevant protein subnetworks and drug-target interactions¹⁶⁵. Recently, this workflow has evolved into advanced integrative pipelines like the SynGeNet (Synergy from Gene expression and Network mining) method, which combines transcriptomic expression signatures, PPI network topology, and drug-target information to

predict synergistic multi-drug combinations for specific genomic contexts¹⁶⁶. The primary strength of the *In Silico* Continuum lies in its unique capacity to couple statistical data power with the formal biophysical logic of mechanistic frameworks, such as Systems Biology and Mechanobiology, which describe complex biological phenomena under strict physiological, fluid-dynamic, and physical constraints^{79,97}. This synthesis is further solidified by Interpretable Machine Learning architectures (e.g., PI-ML and PINNs) that embed governing differential equations directly into neural loss functions, ensuring that AI predictions remain physically consistent and biologically plausible^{112,115}. Crucially, continuous and discrete Simulation techniques—such as Monte Carlo, CA, and Finite Element Modeling—act as the numerical execution engines that operationalize these multi-scale models across computational pipelines^{121,122}. Advanced models can thus describe specific pathological mechanisms by seamlessly blending different computational methods, allowing for the direct estimation of key systemic features—such as steady-state stability, sensitivities, and elasticities—while facilitating quantitative cross-scale validation.

b. Technical limitations and failures Yet, despite their ability to combine diverse methodologies, these multi-layered pipelines face severe technical and scientific hurdles regarding data heterogeneity, mathematical consistency, and the curse of dimensionality. Combining high-throughput genomic sequencing with multi-scale clinical imaging data often triggers the curse of dimensionality—where increasing numbers of variables reduce the efficiency and reliability of data analysis—, which drastically reduces the signal-to-noise ratio. From a numerical perspective, coupling mechanistic ODEs for local dynamics with discrete network topologies for global mobility^{34,167} demands rigorous management of differing temporal scales and spatial resolutions to prevent numerical instability or non-physical gradient vanishing. Furthermore, large-scale mechanistic models offer high explainability under minimal data requirements, but at the cost of significantly higher computational overhead, severe parameter identifiability bottlenecks, and lower scalability across heterogeneous biological systems⁸⁷.

c. Appropriate use cases and recommended contexts The integrated continuum approaches are highly successful and strongly recommended for multi-target drug discovery, multi-scale disease profiling, and the optimization of comprehensive public health containment policies. They excel in high-stakes biomedical scenarios where single-scale predictions fail, allowing researchers to evaluate how molecular network alterations cascade into physical tissue remodeling, or how individual patient-level contact behaviors dynamically interface with macroscale demographic and environmental data streams.

d. Failures and non-recommended contexts Conversely, these complex integrated pipelines fail or are strongly discouraged when applied to urgent clinical scenarios where data is highly fragmented or lacks compliance with standardized, interoperable formats adhering to the FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) principles²². Because multidisciplinary pipelines are heavily tailored to the

specific datasets, regional mobility matrices, or healthcare infrastructures used during initial calibration, they are highly sensitive to data drift. When exposed to alternative patient populations or shifting socio-demographic contexts, the compounding uncertainty across uncalibrated model interfaces triggers a geometric accumulation of errors, reducing model portability and rendering the multi-scale integrated outputs ungeneralizable outside their native training environments¹¹⁰.

e. Clinical translation and current status Currently, the clinical readiness of an *in silico* method is intrinsically linked to its intended translational use case, as mapped out in the decision-making roadmap of Fig. 3. Pattern-recognition and diagnostic screening tasks have seen rapid clinical adoption of Bioinformatics and Black-box medicine due to their empirical success in processing electronic health records and diagnostic imaging. However, intervention-design tasks require the higher fidelity of integrative and mechanistic frameworks. The ultimate goal of the *In Silico* Continuum remains the complete synthesis of these diverse scales into virtual patients and digital twins, ensuring that clinical interventions are optimized, safe, and biologically transparent.

f. Illustrative example: The Virtual Brain A representative case of successful multidisciplinary integration that embodies the *in silico* continuum is The Virtual Brain (TVB) platform, which builds personalized digital brain twins to improve neuroscience and neurology, for instance to optimize surgical interventions in drug-resistant focal epilepsy^{168,169}. In this paradigm, the computational pipeline systematically integrates various methodologies and uses multi-modal patient data to bridge separate biophysical scales. The workflow begins at the structural network layer by processing individual diffusion-weighted Magnetic Resonance Imaging (d-MRI) to map patient-specific white matter tractography and structural connectome matrices^{168,170}. To operationalize this static network topology into a dynamic system, the pipeline embeds a mechanistic neural mass model—governed by non-linear ordinary differential equations (such as the five-variable Epileptor framework¹⁷¹)—into each anatomical graph node to simulate local neural population oscillations and seizure-recruitment kinetics. To align simulations with clinical endpoints, a machine learning Bayesian inversion framework (utilizing advanced sampling algorithms like the No-U-Turn Sampler) is implemented to estimate latent spatial parameters, such as the individualized degree of epileptogenicity across distinct brain regions, bypassing parameter-starved limitations through mathematical model inversion of patient-specific seizure propagation data¹⁷². The translational and predictive utility of this integrated continuum was profoundly quantified in clinical cohort studies: the computational framework achieved a 77% precision rate in detecting the epileptogenic zone network in patients who achieved post-operative seizure-free status, demonstrating that regions defined as epileptogenic exclusively by the model significantly correlate with surgical outcomes and residual seizure generation when left un-resected¹⁷³. This platform has advanced into large-scale, multi-center prospective clinical trials (such as EPINOV, NCT03643016), demonstrating how coupling statistical machine learning inversion with multi-scale network

mechanics can directly guide neurosurgical planning and dramatically improve postoperative outcomes for complex neurological disorders^{169,173}.

V. CHALLENGE: WHAT MAKES A MODEL VALUABLE?

TABLE II. Essential characteristics of a valuable *in silico* model, with descriptions and illustrative examples.

Feature	Description	Example
Informative	Generates new hypotheses, explains mechanisms, and reveals discrepancies	Zucker rat model for obesity and hypertension
Tractable	Computationally feasible, analytically interpretable, and parameter-efficient	Non-dimensionalized ODE models
Predictive	Mechanistic understanding allowing extrapolation beyond observed data	Multiscale models of tissue growth
Well-posed	Solutions exist, are unique, and stable under parameter and input perturbations	Models with controlled boundary conditions
Reproducible	Methods, data, and results can be independently validated worldwide	Open code and FAIR datasets in published models
Clinically translatable	Outputs are interpretable, actionable, and validated	Distinguish recurrence and necrosis in brain metastasis

Assessing the value of an *in silico* model requires careful consideration of its domain of use, operational objectives, and target questions. Rather than striving for an exhaustive replication of biological complexity, a model’s utility depends on specific structural and predictive criteria synthesized in Figure 4 and Table II.

Computational frameworks are traditionally deployed to formalize healthy and pathological states, systemic responses to interventions, and physiological dynamics¹⁷⁴. Beyond merely reproducing experimental data, the primary metric of a model’s value lies in generating predictions grounded in mechanistic biophysical insights. Crucially, systematic deviations from observed behaviors are often equally informative, as these mismatches expose flaws in current biological assumptions and drive iterative workflows where simulation failures directly motivate new experimental setups.

The heuristic value of a model does not strictly depend on its exact structural or genetic relevance to a human pathology. For instance, the obese Zucker rat model—characterized by a missense mutation in the long-chain leptin receptor—remains a fundamental tool for studying obesity-related hypertension, despite the rarity of such mutations in clinical populations^{175,176}. Its scientific utility lies in its biophysical capacity to isolate and interrogate specific causal pathways, thereby establishing clear boundary conditions for experimental and therapeutic design.

FIG. 4. Key characteristics and examples that confer value to an *in silico* model.

To transition from academic heuristics to actionable clinical applications, model reproducibility and mathematical well-posedness are paramount. Independent investigators must be capable of replicating simulation trajectories within acceptable confidence intervals, necessitating transparent open-source methodologies, data-sharing infrastructures, and FAIR-compliant publication practices^{22,177}. From an engineering perspective, this reliability is governed by well-posedness—ensuring the existence, uniqueness, and stability of solutions under numerical perturbations¹⁷⁸. Ill-posed models may easily replicate a specific calibration dataset through unconstrained parameter optimization, but they routinely lack generalizability and predictive power when exposed to novel boundary conditions.

Consequently, effective models must balance biological complexity with mathematical tractability. High-fidelity architectures must navigate intrinsic biophysical challenges, including multi-scale dynamics, non-linear feedbacks, and emergent properties, by enforcing strict parameter economy to remain identifiable and testable given data constraints¹⁷⁸. Analytical techniques such as non-dimensionalization and scaling are essential to reduce parameter spaces, mitigating overfitting while capturing core system dynamics.

Ultimately, within medical and regulatory domains, validation cannot remain a purely qualitative exercise; without formal verification and validation (V&V), computational frameworks lack recognized predictive credibility^{23,24}. To bridge the historical disconnect between academic modeling and clinical implementation, the scientific community increasingly relies on formalized verification, validation, and uncertainty quantification (VVUQ) standards, such as the ASME V&V 40 framework⁹. Under these regulatory guidelines, a model’s credibility is assessed in direct relation to its specific Context of Use (COU), ensuring that the mathematical precision of the tool is commensurate with the clinical risk of the decision it supports^{10,19}.

In biomedical settings, this credibility must seamlessly align with clinical translatability. A model may be mechanistically elegant yet clinically irrelevant if its outputs are not interpretable, actionable, or robustly validated across heterogeneous patient populations. Bridging this translation gap requires a strict alignment between modeling objectives, data

availability, regulatory constraints, and clinical workflows. A prominent contemporary example is the open-access predictive calculator developed by Ocaña *et al.*¹⁷⁹, which computes the probability of radiation necrosis in brain metastases following apparent tumor regrowth. By utilizing a multivariable mechanistic model that integrates primary tumor histology, radiation fractionation schemes, and volumetric growth exponents across three post-irradiation time points, this tool converts complex non-linear growth kinetics into actionable, transparent clinical insights.

In conclusion, particularly in biomedical and clinical contexts, a valuable model is informative, predictive, tractable, yet sufficiently detailed, well-posed, reproducible, validated, and clinically translatable (Figure 4 and Table II). Above all, it must generate meaningful, biophysically grounded insights that advance understanding and directly guide experimentation, clinical interventions, and regulatory decision-making.

VI. VIRTUAL CLINIC

Following the overview of disease modeling principles, this section introduces the virtual clinic framework (Fig. 5, Table III), a paradigm that leverages *in silico* models and data of patients to simulate disease progression and translate computationally optimized therapies to real patients. To build this operational testing environment, Virtual Patient Models (VPMs) integrate heterogeneous clinical data through robust parameter identification, scaling from individual virtual patients to comprehensive virtual cohorts that undergo rigorous validation, analysis, and algorithmic control. In practice, this framework is ideally deployed both prior to and during medical interventions, continuously refined by real-world outcomes and applied to patient-specific data sourced from clinical collaborators or public repositories.

FIG. 5. Schematic representation of the virtual clinic framework, illustrating the relationships between patient data, virtual patient (or digital twins), virtual cohorts, simulation and control, clinical support, and experimental validation.

A. Virtual patient models

This section presents the key aspects of VPMs, which could be considered a patient-specific instance of *in silico* modeling of complex diseases. Indeed, VPMs are calibrated on real patient data to create virtual patients (VPs) describing real patients, or virtual populations in which each VP is individually described, thus remaining at the patient level.

A VPM is an advanced computer-based simulation emulating real patients used for healthcare, such as medical education¹⁸⁰, training¹⁸¹, generating synthetic data¹⁸², and research¹⁸³. It replicates human behaviors, anatomy, physiology, pathology, and clinical features, simulating various medical conditions and treatment responses. For VPMs that operate at cellular or tissue scales, discrete frameworks such as CA and ABM are often the natural choice because they explicitly represent individual cells and local interactions; these discrete approaches can be hybridized with continuum descriptions (e.g., PDEs for diffusive fields) when micro–macro coupling is needed. CA/ABM-based VPMs therefore demand higher-resolution biological and biomarker data for calibration but can capture spatial heterogeneity and emergent behaviors crucial for some clinical questions^{45,102,128}.

In modern applications, VPMs explicitly link internal model states to measurable clinical data or biomarkers, which serve as observable quantities connecting simulated physiology with patient data. These biomarkers may be molecular (e.g., gene expression signatures, circulating tumor DNA), imaging-derived, physiological, or digital, depending on the disease and modeling scale. For example, Dillenseger *et al.* reviewed the role of digital biomarkers in multiple sclerosis¹⁸⁴. Hervas-Raluy *et al.*¹⁸⁵ integrated in their computational patient-specific models the distribution of cell density, tumor vasculature, and tumor geometry from clinical MRI imaging data, clearly contributing to create more physiological models. Imaging biomarkers may be extracted through mathematical image analysis or obtained by directly comparing VPM outputs with clinical imaging data^{32,186}.

An ideal VPM should possess the following attributes¹⁸⁷.

Physiological Relevance. VPMs must capture essential physiological dynamics with medical sensor-like accuracy, establishing a minimum baseline of mechanistic complexity.

Clinical Relevance. Models must operate within clinical timeframes, utilizing readily measurable inputs and outputs to guide real-time care. This clinical utility defines an upper bound on optimal complexity, ensuring the framework remains practical and accessible for frontline clinicians.

Identifiable Treatment Sensitivity. VPMs must precisely predict patient-specific responses to therapeutic inputs, maintaining a well-defined rate of change in output values relative to variations in input parameters.

Clinical Data Identifiability. Model parameters must be uniquely identifiable using data accessible at the bedside within a clinically relevant timeframe. While current data constraints limit model complexity for direct clinical deployment, maintaining unique identifiability prevents overfitting and ensures robustness. Crucially, as longitudinal data availability expands, these architectures can be dynamically updated to incorporate more complex, patient-specific biophysical dynamics, ultimately facilitating optimal, personalized therapy.

B. Data required

VPMs and clinical data are used via calibration or systems identification to derive VPs¹⁸⁷. The relevant input and output

data should be measured to identify sensitivities accurately. In this context, biomarkers play a central role as calibration targets, constraining patient-specific parameters through longitudinal or cross-sectional measurements. Biomarker-driven calibration is particularly relevant when direct measurement of internal physiological states is not feasible, making biomarkers surrogate observables for latent model variables^{188,189}. The frequency of data collection should match the dynamics of the patients' conditions and clinical interventions: clearly, faster-changing dynamics require more frequent data collection. Electronic interfaces and automated sensing, for example, polysomnographic or sleep technology used for studying restless legs syndrome³⁵, offer opportunities for continuous data collection, which is impossible in many diseases, such as cancers and COVID-19. However, sufficient and relevant data are available for many VPMs. Researchers should consider and pursue data sharing to enhance research gains using big data informatics and ML. Data sharing initiatives, like the GEO (Gene Expression Omnibus)¹⁹⁰ and TCGA (The Cancer Genome Atlas)¹⁹¹ database in the context of cancer research, are necessary for improving *in silico* medicine.

Biomarkers are central to the construction, stratification, and validation of VPMs. Molecular biomarkers (genomic, transcriptomic, proteomic) can parameterize patient-specific pathway or disease-state variables; imaging biomarkers provide spatial and structural constraints (important for CA/ABM or hybrid tissue models); physiological biomarkers (vital signs, lab tests) feed real-time state updates; and digital biomarkers (wearables, passive monitoring) enable longitudinal model updating and closed-loop control. The careful selection and harmonization of biomarkers across modalities improves identifiability, supports subgroup stratification within virtual cohorts, and provides objective endpoints for model validation^{3,192,193}.

C. Virtual patients and digital twins

The process of creating VPs essentially consists of selecting or developing a VPM, collecting patient-specific data, and using these data to calibrate the chosen VPM. Model selection and data collection are interchangeable and sometimes recursive steps based on the specific investigation. In this way, model investigations provide both valuable clinical and physiological insights. Therefore, they can assess biological assumptions, evaluate the influence of normal or aberrant physiology, and gauge the effects of sensing or delivery technologies¹⁸⁷.

The methodologies employed to create VPs are rooted in years of physiological modeling and parameter estimations for research investigations¹⁸⁷. VPs effectively capture single patient trials *in silico*^{143,183} and can be employed in real-time for personalized^{3,194}, model-based protocols, tailoring treatment uniquely for each individual patient, thus, improving currently adopted one-size-fits-all treatment strategy^{187,195}. Indeed, VPs represent specific patient responses encoded by the model structure and identified parameters from patient data. These responses are typically linked to patient-specific

biomarker trajectories, allowing the digital twin to remain synchronized with the evolving biological state of the real patient over time^{155,196}. Comparing model evolution across different conditions enhances understanding, such as comparing patients with and without specific drug therapy, but also responses of different patients under the same therapy^{143,187}.

In such a personalized context, the VP is referred to as a Digital Twin (DT)^{194,196–198}. Originally adopted in the automotive industry to simulate real-world system behavior through the integration of components and their interactions, the DT concept has been progressively translated into medicine. Recent perspectives further describe DTs as dynamically updated patient-specific computational representations integrating mechanistic modeling with longitudinal clinical data to support personalized prediction and decision-making⁴. In biomedical applications, DTs often represent patient-specific organs reconstructed from detailed imaging data^{3,193} and integrate multiscale information linking structure and physiological function, from cells and tissues to entire organs. By enabling *in silico* experimentation under controlled and repeatable conditions, DTs allow investigations and subgroup analyses that would be impractical, risky, or ethically challenging to perform directly in patients, thereby supporting personalized medicine and clinical decision-making^{194,196–198}.

Practically, the maturity and clinical relevance of a DT depend on (i) the fidelity of the underlying mechanistic and/or data-driven models, (ii) the availability and temporal resolution of biomarkers and clinical data for online synchronization, and (iii) robust uncertainty quantification and validation pipelines to establish trust for clinical decision support and regulatory acceptance^{3,192}.

D. Virtual cohorts

Virtual cohorts consist of sets of VPs or DTs. Inter-patient variability within virtual cohorts is often characterized through distributions of model parameters and of clinically observed biomarkers, capturing molecular, phenotypic, and functional heterogeneity observed in real populations¹⁹⁹. Cohorts can be designed to be specific or general (the latter has typically larger utility), encompassing various patient states and dynamics really observed. Accurate protocol design and robust results in deployment depend on representing all clinically relevant patient dynamics. Virtual cohorts should have sufficient patients and diagnoses, reflecting real hospital practice for reliable virtual trials²⁰⁰.

The significance of virtual cohorts lies in their relevance to research, as limited clinical trial cohorts may not generalize well to diverse care situations. Virtual cohorts allow *in silico* trials, facilitating the design of compelling and general protocols applicable to various cohorts encountered in practice, instilling confidence in their universal applicability, reducing costs and risks for real patients²⁰¹. Well-constructed virtual cohorts use stratification criteria based on clinical and biomarker-derived features to ensure representation of relevant subpopulations and to enable subgroup-specific *in silico*

TABLE III. Key components of the virtual clinic, their definitions, and the insights or purposes they provide. Together, these elements enable *in silico* experiments and personalized treatment optimization.

Component	Description	Purpose / Insights
Virtual Patient Models (VPMs)	Patient-specific models calibrated from clinical and physiological data	Provide mechanistic and clinically relevant foundation for simulations
Patient data collection	Acquisition of bedside, sensor, imaging, or omics data and biomarkers	Enables parameter identification and model personalization
Virtual Patients (VPs) & Digital Twins (DTs)	Individualized patient models and simulations derived from VPMs and patient data	Predict treatment responses, test hypotheses, and tailor therapies
Virtual Cohorts (VCs)	Sets of VPs representing populations with diverse clinical characteristics	Support virtual clinical trials, protocol testing, and generalizable insights
Validation	Comparing <i>in silico</i> and real results at patient- and cohort-level	Ensures model reliability, predictive accuracy, and trustworthiness
Virtual analysis	<i>In silico</i> experiments and simulations	Explore disease progression, patient responses, and treatment optimization
Virtual control	Open- and closed-loop control, model predictive control (MPC)	Guides decision-making, optimizes and adapts therapies, and supports personalization

testing and power analyses^{3,202}. This approach results in a one-method-fits-all—a model-based and personalized form of care that fits all patients—providing greater confidence in the universality of the results¹⁸⁷.

E. Validation

The primary concern with any modeling approach is validating whether the VPM accurately captures and predicts clinically pertinent dynamics. A successful retrospective calibration, or simple data-fitting, does not guarantee that the identified parameters and the resulting VP possess the generalization capability required to faithfully predict responses to novel therapeutic interventions⁶. Indeed, the most practical and reliable way to test VPM validity and the identified VP parameter values is to assess model predictions in response to new clinical inputs.

VPMs and their clinical applicability can be validated through three progressive validation tests¹⁸⁷.

- 1. Patient-level validation.** A patient-specific model is developed using clinical data from a baseline monitoring period, and subsequent independent, out-of-sample clinical inputs are simulated. The predicted outputs are compared to the actual measured patient data, validating the predictive ability of the VPM. Crucially, this step moves beyond simple data-model alignment by utilizing a strict temporal split where the validation dataset represents an unobserved future state or a distinct therapeutic perturbation. In practice, validation is frequently performed using biomarker-based endpoints, including longitudinal biomarker trajectories and clinically established surrogate endpoints, rather than raw internal model states²⁰³.
- 2. Cohort-level validation.** Using a virtual cohort, a specific protocol is simulated, and outcomes are compared to those observed in real clinic¹⁴³. Statistical results are

compared, validating the model and parameter identification methods over the entire cohort and individual patients.

- 3. Cohort-level cross-validation.** Multiple clinically matched cohorts are used to create virtual cohorts, which are then tested with well-known cross-validation procedures, i.e., performing the protocol of one cohort on the other cohorts. Simulations are compared with clinical data from matched cohorts, assessing the independence and accuracy of patient-specific, model-based sensitivities and their trustworthiness to produce real results when treated with different protocols.

These validation tests provide a comprehensive assessment of the VPMs, ensuring their reliability and effectiveness in predicting personalized care. At the patient level, the precision of simulations and predictions is based on the ability of the model to capture fluctuations in the conditions of the patient. Stochastic models can be employed to assess the potential range of intra-patient variability, offering estimates of this variability²⁰⁴.

F. Virtual analysis

Virtual analysis refers to the use of computer-based modeling and simulation techniques to analyze VPs (or DTs) and virtual cohorts, i.e., perform *in silico* experiments. In this setting, ABMs are particularly valuable to explore how local cellular interactions give rise to emergent biomarker patterns at the tissue or systemic level^{42,205}. After designing suitable VPMs calibrated on patient-specific data to obtain VPs, virtual analysis involves using computational simulations and algorithms to study behavior under specific medical conditions, how behaviors change based on different conditions, make predictions, and gain new insights^{143,200}.

It allows researchers and clinicians to explore the difference between healthy and pathological states, patient characteristics, interactions between drugs and biological systems,

understand disease progression, evaluate treatments by predicting their outcomes, and external or environmental factors on the specific problem under investigation.

It is important to note that virtual analysis complements and supports laboratory studies and can provide valuable insights and hypotheses that guide further experimentation. It also enables the use of virtual cohorts to perform trial simulations, sample size and power assessments, and sensitivity analyses before committing to real-world trials—thereby reducing costs and risks associated with early-stage clinical research^{3,6,19,201}. However, it is not a perfect substitute nowadays for clinical trials or real-world validation, and its predictions and findings should be interpreted with caution.

G. Virtual control

In *in silico* medicine, virtual control refers to the application of computational models, control theory principles, and simulations to govern biological processes—such as neuronal behavior²⁰⁶—or to optimize clinical decision-making, including vaccination strategies¹⁰⁵ and oncological therapies^{195,207}. Driven by the escalating demands of aging populations, chronic diseases, and resource constraints, integrating automation and digital technologies into healthcare is essential to enhance patient outcomes¹⁹⁸. Virtual control frameworks accomplish this by predicting patient outcomes under untreated or standard-of-care baselines²⁰⁸, systematically evaluating variables like drug dosage, timing, and resource allocation to identify optimal, patient-specific strategies.

The paradigm relies on two foundational control architectures: open-loop and closed-loop systems. Open-loop control executes a predefined treatment plan without real-time adjustments based on the disease course, offering simplicity, predictability, and ease of implementation. This architecture is typically reserved for highly predictable standard procedures, such as specific surgical interventions, or theoretical treatment studies where real-time clinical monitoring is unfeasible^{93,143,195,209,210}. For instance, in neuroblastoma treatment modeling, open-loop control has been deployed to mimic patient-specific tumor heterogeneity and optimize drug efficacy, demonstrating superior outcomes compared to traditional one-size-fits-all protocols¹⁹⁵. Conversely, closed-loop (or feedback) control provides adaptability by monitoring dynamic patient states, device metrics, or treatment responses to iteratively adjust interventions^{211–215}. This responsive approach is vital for volatile conditions like cancer or diabetes, where longitudinal biomarkers serve as essential feedback signals to close the loop^{216,217}. A widely adopted closed-loop technique is Model Predictive Control (MPC)^{218–222}. Unlike static linear-quadratic regulators, MPC optimizes a finite time horizon but executes control actions only within the current interval, performing iterative re-optimizations to account for future system states.

While virtual control offers a transformative framework for mechanistic inquiry, therapy optimization, and personalized medicine, its translational reliability ultimately remains

bounded by the mathematical approximations, underlying assumptions, and data quality of the predictive models.

H. Examples

The operationalization of the *in silico* continuum and the implementation of virtual clinics have recently moved from theoretical frameworks to validated clinical applications across diverse medical domains. This section examines three pivotal case studies that demonstrate how the virtual clinic can be used to enhance patient outcomes retrospectively by aiding in diagnostic and mechanistic classification, prospectively by directly guiding interventional therapies, and at the population level by supporting conventional clinical trial cohorts.

The development of organ-level DTs within the gastrointestinal tract has transitioned abstract computational physiology into rigorous diagnostic and predictive platforms capable of optimizing phenotype classification and exploring surgical outcomes^{223,224}. Pioneered by Pandolfino and Patankar, this framework couples non-linear continuum mechanics with data-driven neural layers to simulate multiphase fluid-structure interactions (FSI) and active tissue deformations during bolus transport^{225,226}. The core biophysical software couples the Navier-Stokes equations for the fluid phase with the dynamic stress equilibrium of the deformed esophageal wall²²⁵. To model the continuous feedback between these organ-level physical deformations and underlying neural control, Elisha et al. formalized an empirically guided neuromechanical digital twin of the esophagus²²⁴. This architecture models the enteric nervous system as a network of unidirectionally coupled relaxation oscillators activated by intrinsic, distension-sensitive mechanoreceptors, demonstrating how normal repetitive antegrade contractions or pathological retrograde spasms emerge naturally from alterations in mechanoreceptor thresholds.

To personalize these generalized domains into individual patient twins, the framework's free parameters are calibrated via mechanics-informed machine learning using patient-specific functional luminal imaging probe cross-sectional profiles and high-resolution manometry data²²³. Using these real-world data streams as inverse modeling boundaries, surgeons can simulate virtual peroral endoscopic myotomies *in silico*, varying incision lengths and spatial orientations to balance post-surgical bolus clearance against the risk of lower sphincter incompetence²²⁶. Clinically, this validated calibration offers a rigorous translation pathway by exposing previously unmeasurable physiological markers, such as localized tissue stiffness and neural tone variations, across different patient cohorts²²³. Furthermore, by characterizing the mechanical dysfunction and pre-calculating the impact of incision envelopes on bolus transport metrics, this framework provides a biophysical rationale to optimize patient stratification and potentially minimize risks of incomplete symptom relief or post-operative reflux in future targeted interventions^{224,226}.

In a prospective approach, personalized heart digital twins represent a transformative milestone in cardiac electrophysiology by translating non-invasive clinical modalities into

predictive interventions. Developed by the Trayanova Lab at Johns Hopkins University, this multiscale computational framework solves continuous reaction-diffusion PDEs governing cardiac tissue excitability and spatio-temporal electrical wavefront propagation, allowing for the integration of structural remodeling²²⁷, drug-channel kinetics²²⁸, and genotype-specific profiles²²⁹. The foundational dependence of these biophysical predictions on geometric grid resolution was systematically exposed by O'Hara et al.²²⁷. In post-infarction patients, they implemented an oversampling short-axis late gadolinium-enhanced cardiac magnetic resonance (LGE-CMR) technique, combining two subsequent clinical-resolution scans to collapse the virtual slice thickness from 6 mm to 3 mm²²⁷. This spatial refinement drastically minimized partial volume effects at the infarct borders, increasing the digital twin's predictive accuracy for unique ventricular tachycardia (VT) reentrant circuits from 54.5% to 66.6% ($P < 0.01$) against clinical electroanatomic data, and demonstrating that identifying emergent post-ablation VT depends strictly on sub-millimeter structural fidelity²²⁷.

Building upon this high-fidelity substrate representation, Brody et al. utilized 7 patient-specific ischemic digital twins to isolate how concomitant amiodarone (AMD) alters electroanatomic mapping (EAM) signatures at two therapeutic concentrations²²⁸. The simulations revealed that while AMD did not significantly change overall VT inducibility, it altered circuit morphology, prolonged cycle lengths, and expanded regions classified as abnormal by low-voltage, prolonged-duration, and high-fractionation criteria, thereby reducing mapping specificity and potentially obscuring ablation targets²²⁸. Crucially, the digital twins demonstrated that functional mapping markers—specifically Isochronal Crowding (IC) zones—remained highly targeted within 9 mm of the critical isthmus and were not expanded by the drug²²⁸. By combining multiple-wavefront pacing orientations, the framework markedly improved IC colocalization without loss of specificity, establishing a biophysically validated mapping strategy when antiarrhythmic medication cannot be withdrawn²²⁸.

Finally, expanding the continuum from pharmacology to inherited channelopathies, Zhang et al. introduced the GenDIRECT framework, which couples image-derived structural remodeling with desmosomal genetic profiling (θ_{gene}) for patients with Arrhythmogenic Right Ventricular Cardiomyopathy (ARVC)²²⁹. Evaluating 30 ARVC patients across two common genotypes (*PKP2* and *PLN/DES* variants), the virtual heart simulations subjected the genotype-specific domains to multi-site rapid pacing to uncover structural reentrant channels. The predicted ablation targets achieved an outstanding overlap with successful clinical lesion zones (Dice score = 89.47%) while revealing that optimal virtual ablation paths required significantly smaller lesion volumes ($P = 5.39 \times 10^{-5}$). For patients exhibiting intraprocedural VT recurrence within 12 months, the digital twin successfully anticipated the expanded substrate, matching the combined lesions of both the initial and repeat clinical procedures, and effectively eliminating VT inducibility across all virtual pacing protocols²²⁹.

Finally, we discuss implementation of *in silico* trial. Con-

ventional clinical trial designs systematically fail in pediatric and rare disease cohorts due to recruitment bottlenecks, high screen-failure rates, and early study discontinuation, resulting in underpowered studies, prohibitive costs, and the unethical exposure of vulnerable populations to unproven therapies or placebos^{230,231}. Integrating the *in silico* continuum—via generative prognostic virtual patients, synthetic data substrates, and virtual control arms—circumvents these structural barriers by passing baseline demographic and clinical covariates through validated causal disease-progression models²³⁰. This mathematical framework compresses trial durations, accelerates regulatory approvals, and minimizes human placebo requirements, thereby de-risking live clinical investigations, reducing ethical exposure to potentially harmful interventions, and providing a scalable pathway toward hyper-personalized treatment options²³⁰.

The translational feasibility of this population-scale computational architecture was empirically validated by Li et al. in the context of chronic graft-versus-host disease (cGvHD)²³¹. Utilizing the *Trial Accelerator™* platform, they leveraged historical clinical trial data to construct a first-line treatment cGvHD digital twin cohort (*fiGvHD DT*) of 2,042 virtual patients across 32 cohorts²³¹. The generative model accurately reproduced established clinical baselines, capturing a mean disease onset at 7.58 months post-allogeneic hematopoietic cell transplantation. From this domain, a derived virtual standard-of-care arm (*fiGvHD DT SOC*) of 438 virtual patients across 8 cohorts simulated longitudinal responses to prednisone, predicting a six-month overall response rate (ORR) of 52.7%²³¹. This absolute statistical concordance with empirical literature demonstrates that data-driven synthetic comparators can effectively substitute traditional control groups, provided that ongoing ethical, data privacy, and regulatory criteria are strictly satisfied to ensure synthetic cohorts meet identical evidentiary standards as biological controls^{230,231}.

VII. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In silico methodologies in computational medicine are rapidly evolving from isolated modeling approaches toward integrated frameworks capable of representing complex disease dynamics across multiple biological scales. Despite significant progress in areas such as network-based modeling, systems biology, mechanobiological simulations, and interpretable ML, several fundamental challenges remain. Table summarizes the main advantages and disadvantages of *in silico* medicine. A central limitation lies in the difficulty of achieving consistent multiscale integration, where molecular, cellular, tissue, and clinical data can be combined within coherent and computationally tractable models. In addition, model validation remains a critical bottleneck, particularly in settings where ground truth is partially observable or inherently stochastic. These issues are further compounded by heterogeneity across patients and the intrinsic nonlinearity of disease progression.

Emerging directions in the field are increasingly focused

TABLE IV. Conceptual summary of the main advantages and challenges of *in silico* methodologies in computational medicine.

Advantages		Disadvantages	
Theme	Description	Theme	Description
Virtual experiments	Controlled, ethical, and customizable environments for hypothesis testing, high-throughput screening, and rare-event exploration ^{232,233} .	Computational Complexity	Multiscale dynamics and high-resolution spatial models introduce severe computational bottlenecks and strict accuracy–tractability trade-offs ^{234,235} .
Predictive decision-making	Proactive treatment scheduling, drug response optimization, and mitigation of therapy failures ²³⁶ .	Data dependency & quality	Performance strongly relies on data standardization, quality, and the scarce availability of extensive longitudinal datasets ²² .
System-level modeling	Integration of extensive parameter spaces capturing organism-wide homeostasis, infection, and evolutionary dynamics ¹⁷ .	Parameter uncertainty	High variability in parameter estimation and biomarker profiles undermines model robustness, potentially leading to overfitting.
Multiscale integration	Mechanistic coupling of molecular, cellular, tissue, and organismal dynamics across varied temporal scales ²³⁷ .	Domain shift & transferability	Models often fail to generalize across different clinical centers, species, patient demographics, or disease phenotypes ^{108,238} .
Spatial heterogeneity	Agent-based (AB), cellular automata (CA), and hybrid continuum frameworks capture emergent clinical dynamics ^{45,102,128} .	Interpretability constraints	Black-box AI/ML architectures lack mechanistic transparency, limiting clinical trust and causative attribution ¹⁷ .
Resource efficiency	Drastic reduction in experimental costs, accelerated drug development timelines, and minimized animal testing.	Validation deficits	The lack of independent, high-quality benchmark datasets complicates rigorous validation and uncertainty quantification ^{8,9,19} .
Reproducibility & collaboration	Standardized model sharing and open refinement foster interdisciplinary transparency and scientific collaboration.	Clinical translation	Translation into real-world workflows is severely hindered by low system interoperability and EHR compatibility barriers ²³⁹ .
Data visualization	Multimodal data integration combined with advanced visualization tools to support clinical deployment.	Regulatory & ethical barriers	Slow standardization for software-as-a-medical-device frameworks and clinical accountability concerns ^{9,240} .

on bridging mechanistic and data-driven paradigms. Hybrid physics informed-AI and interpretable ML models represent a particularly promising avenue, as they combine the interpretability and structural constraints of mechanistic approaches with the flexibility and predictive power of machine learning techniques. In parallel, the concept of virtual patients and digital twins is transitioning from conceptual frameworks toward more operational tools, enabling patient-specific simulation and hypothesis testing *in silico*. However, the translation of these models into regulatory-grade digital twins requires robust strategies for uncertainty quantification, interpretability, and longitudinal validation, ensuring that predictions remain reliable under clinically relevant variability. This is particularly relevant in contexts such as treatment optimization and therapy response prediction, where mechanistic simulation is increasingly used to support decision-making processes.

A further key direction concerns uncertainty-aware clinical prediction and the systematic integration of heterogeneous biomedical data. The increasing availability of large-scale resources, ranging from omics repositories such as The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA)²⁴¹ and Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO)²⁴² to imaging-derived biomarkers and digital clinical signatures, opens the possibility of constructing unified modeling frameworks that operate across scales and modalities. Achieving this integration will require not only methodological advances but also standardization in data representation and model interoperability.

Current efforts to address these challenges are increas-

ingly focused on the development of standardized validation pipelines, uncertainty quantification frameworks, interoperable biomedical data infrastructures, and hybrid mechanistic–AI architectures capable of integrating heterogeneous patient-specific information. In parallel, advances in scientific machine learning and regulatory-oriented *in silico* trial methodologies are progressively improving the scalability, reproducibility, and clinical credibility of computational medicine frameworks.

Overall, the future of *in silico* medicine is likely to be defined by the convergence of mechanistic modeling, statistical learning, and data-intensive biomedical science, enabling the development of predictive and controllable virtual clinics capable of addressing complex diseases in a personalized and quantitatively rigorous manner.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of interest statement

The Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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